

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARticle Data (SPEARHEAD)

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable 3.5

Cross-calibration of SOHO/ERNE with SOHO/EPHIN

EU's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme

Grant Agreement 101135044

UNIVERSITY
OF TURKU

Kiel University
Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel

UNIVERSITY
OF OULU

Lead Beneficiary	<i>University of Turku</i>
Authors	J. Gieseler, C. Ngom, P. Oleynik, C. Palmroos, A. Fedeli, B. Heber, M. Hörlock & R. Vainio

Work Package	WP3: Cross- and re-calibration
Task	Task 3.7
Deliverable	D3.5: Cross-calibration of SOHO/ERNE with SOHO/EPHIN
Date for Deliverable	29 August 2025

Change Log				
Version	Date	Author(s)	Reason for Modification	Status
1	2025-08-29	Gieseler et al.	New Document	Submitted
2				

Dissemination Level	
Public	X
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Contents

Contents	3
List of Figures	5
List of Acronyms	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
Cross-calibration of SOHO/ERNE with SOHO/EPHIN	8
1 Introduction	8
2 Instrumentation	8
2.1 ERNE aboard SOHO	8
2.1.1 ERNE HED instrument	8
2.1.2 Response functions of ERNE / HED	9
2.2 EPHIN aboard SOHO	9
3 Cross-calibration of ERNE with EPHIN	10
4 Conclusions and Outlook	15
Bibliography	17
Appendix	18
A1 SOHO spacecraft model	18
A2 Energy spectrum fitting	18

List of Figures

1	A sketch of the ERNE / HED sensor head.	9
2	Geant4-simulated responses of ERNE AC counters for forward penetrating relativistic protons for different energy deposit thresholds.	10
3	Geant4-simulated responses of ERNE AC counters for backward penetrating relativistic protons for different energy deposit thresholds.	10
4	Geant4-simulated responses of ERNE AC counters for penetrating relativistic protons coming from all directions for different energy deposit thresholds.	11
5	Count rates of ERNE counters $AC1_TOT$, $AC1_D1E > 1.3\text{MeV}$, and $D3$, during 17 May 2012 (left) and 1 Sep 2014 (right) SEP events. Shaded areas indicate the time ranges used to calculate the corresponding EPHIN spectra shown in Figs. 6 and 7.	11
6	EPHIN proton spectra averaged over different periods during 17 May 2012 (left) and 1 Sep 2014 (right) SEP events. The periods are colour coded corresponding to the shaded regions in Fig. 5. The pre-event GCR background is shown by the black spectra in both plots.	12
7	EPHIN background-subtracted proton spectra averaged over different periods during 17 May 2012 (left) and 1 Sep 2014 (right) SEP events. The periods are colour coded corresponding to the shaded regions in Fig. 5. Different power laws have been fitted to the background-subtracted spectra; the type and parameters of the fits are listed in the legend (see Appendix A2 for details). Plotted on top as diamonds with the same colour coding are corresponding ERNE background-subtracted mean intensities that have been calculated using the geometric factor obtained at the end of Sect. 3.	12
8	ERNE counts rates obtained by folding Geant4-simulated response functions for different AC thresholds with EPHIN spectra obtained from 02:00 to 03:00 on 17 May 2012 for protons coming from all directions for counters $AC1_TOT$ (left) and $AC1_D1E > 1.3\text{MeV}$ (right).	13
9	ERNE normalized count rates corresponding to the simulated count rates divided by the average value of the background-subtracted observed count rates for counters $AC1_TOT$ (left) and $AC1_D1E > 1.3\text{MeV}$ (right).	13
10	For selected spectra, AC energy threshold value where the normalized count rate crosses 1 is plotted as a function of the ERNE average observed count rate for counter $AC1_TOT$	14
11	Geant4-simulated responses of ERNE's $AC1_TOT$ counter for penetrating relativistic protons coming from all directions for the energy deposit threshold range in which the modelled and observed ERNE count rates are in agreement.	15
12	Bow-tie analysis of the ERNE simulated response functions for protons coming from all directions at AC energy threshold 8.27 MeV, corresponding to the lowest threshold where the normalized count rate crosses 1 for counter $AC1_TOT$. The upper panel shows the response function in blue (in arbitrary units) and the derived bow-tie formed by the family of differential effective geometric factors $G\delta E$ for different power-law indices (from -4 to -2). The lower panel shows the statistical measure of the bow-tie spreading in standard-deviation units normalized to the deviation of $G\delta E$ at the effective energy E_{eff}	16
13	Differential geometric factor and effective energy of ERNE simulated response functions for protons coming from all directions at different AC energy threshold for counter $AC1_TOT$	16

- 14 A Geant4 visualisation of the SOHO spacecraft model with ERNE onboard. In the right panel, the yellow piece on the top with red spots is the ERNE sensor unit. 18

List of Acronyms

AC	Anti-Coincidence
BGO	Bismuth Germanium Oxide
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
COSTEP	Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer
D	Deliverable
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and electron Experiment
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
Geant4	GEometry ANd Tracking 4
HED	High Energy Detector (of ERNE)
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SOHO	SOlar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports the efforts to cross-correlate the High Energy Detector (HED) of the Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and electron Experiment (ERNE) with the Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN), both aboard the SOlar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO), in order to estimate the unknown energy deposit threshold of the Anti-Coincidence (AC) counters of ERNE. This is needed to extend the range of detectable energies for protons measured by ERNE / HED using previously unused internal counters. Response functions for these channels have been simulated (Köberle et al. 2025) using an updated instrument model (Köberle et al. 2024) within the SPECification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD) project, but still had the AC threshold as an unknown variable. Folding these ERNE response functions to previously verified (Heber et al. 2024) EPHIN >100 MeV proton spectra and then comparing to measured ERNE count rates, the lowest energy threshold for the ERNE AC counters could be estimated to be 8.27 MeV. By applying a bow-tie analysis to the corresponding response function, the effective energy and geometric factor of protons observed in this counter could be determined to be 129.2 MeV and 877.9 cm^2 , respectively, with an accuracy of 1%.

1 Introduction

The publicly available data of [ERNE / HED](#) aboard [SOHO](#) currently extends to ~ 100 MeV for protons. However, the instrument has a number of channels that primarily respond to high-energy protons (hundreds of MeVs) that have so far neither been calibrated nor released. Within the [SPEARHEAD](#) project, the GEometry ANd Tracking 4 ([Geant4](#)) model of the instrument has been updated ([Köberle et al. 2024](#)) and new response functions have been simulated ([Köberle et al. 2025](#)).

Penetrating particles in the detector are identified by detecting a signal in the plastic scintillator [AC](#) detector in the bottom of the detector stack. The detector is read out by photodiodes instead of photomultipliers, and this, unfortunately, leads to a non-ideal detection efficiency of penetrating particles. As plastic scintillators are not very luminous, the effective energy threshold of the detection is larger than a minimally ionising particle can deposit in the detector. Unfortunately, there is no pulse-height data available from the scintillator, and the detection threshold of the comparator signal was also not calibrated on ground prior to the launch. Thus, the threshold of the [ERNE AC](#) counters is not well known, and treated essentially as a free parameter of the instrument response function. In order to obtain real physical quantities from the [ERNE](#) observations, a realistic estimate of this threshold is needed. A set of response functions with feasible threshold levels has been calculated and an in-flight calibration of the detection threshold has been attempted by comparing with different datasets providing fluxes and spectra.

This Deliverable ([D](#)) 3.5 describes the process to achieve this by carrying out an in-flight cross-calibration. For this, we take advantage of the fact that with [EPHIN](#) another detector is aboard [SOHO](#) that provides reliable observations of protons in the same energy range, allowing us to attempt to calibrate [ERNE](#) with the same particle population.

2 Instrumentation

2.1 [ERNE](#) aboard [SOHO](#)

2.1.1 [ERNE HED](#) instrument

The Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and electron Experiment ([ERNE](#); [Valtonen et al. 1997](#)) is one of the scientific payloads aboard [SOHO](#). The instrument layout of [ERNE](#)'s High Energy Detector ([HED](#)) is illustrated in [Fig. 1](#). At the top are the silicon strip detectors [S1x](#), [S1y](#), [S2x](#), and [S2y](#), each with a thickness of $300 \mu\text{m}$. Each layer contains two chips, each measuring $40.4 \text{ mm} \times 81.9 \text{ mm}$, resulting in a combined active geometric area of approximately 46 cm^2 .

Beneath the strip detectors lies the [D1](#) detector, composed of two silicon layers, each $500 \mu\text{m}$ thick, making the total thickness $1000 \mu\text{m}$. Below [D1](#) is the [D2](#) layer, a [CsI\(Tl\)](#) scintillator with an active area of $79.5 \text{ mm} \times 79.5 \text{ mm}$ and a thickness of 8 mm .

Following downward from [D2](#) is the [D3](#) detector, which consists of five Bismuth Germanium Oxide ([BGO](#)) scintillator bars, each with dimensions of $15.4 \text{ mm} \times 15.0 \text{ mm} \times 79.5 \text{ mm}$. Surrounding the detector stack are the Anti-Coincidence ([AC](#)) detectors, made of plastic scintillator plates with a thickness of 5.2 mm . These include two logical Anti-Coincidence detectors: [AC1](#), located at the bottom of the stack, and [AC2](#), positioned along the sides of [D2](#) and [D3](#).

[ERNE / HED](#) model As described in [D2.1](#) ([Köberle et al. 2024](#)), the [Geant4](#) model of [SOHO / ERNE](#) has been reconstructed using the paper drawings archive. Each mechanical part of the instrument was sketched as a 3-D body in the mechanical Computer-Aided Design ([CAD](#)) software. When all parts were completed, the instrument was digitally assembled into a realistic [CAD](#) model with assigned materials. The model was tessellated and converted into Geometry Description Markup Language ([GDML](#)). The

Figure 1: A sketch of the ERNE / HED sensor head.

conversion engine is pyg4ometry¹ (Walker et al. 2022; Boogert et al. 2025).

2.1.2 Response functions of ERNE / HED

We calculated the responses of two penetrating particle counters of ERNE / HED, named AC1_TOT and AC1_D1E>1.3MeV (in Köberle et al. 2024 labelled C16 and C5, respectively). AC1_TOT requires an EVENT condition that is a combination of three valid (single-segment) hits in the position-sensitive layers S1y, S2x, and S2y (see Fig. 1), a hit in the bottom Anti-Coincidence detector AC1, and no hit in the side Anti-Coincidence detectors AC2. AC1_D1E>1.3MeV has the same requirements as AC1_TOT, but in addition requires the deposit in the D1 layer to be above 1.3 MeV.

Since the exact energy deposit threshold of AC1 is not well known, we simulated a set of response functions in Geant4 using a range of plausible AC1 threshold values. Given that AC1 and AC2 are both made of the same plastic scintillator material, we assume they share the same energy threshold. Consequently, in the simulation, the threshold variations of AC1 and AC2 are treated as coupled.

Figure 2 shows the response functions for particles penetrating the whole ERNE sensor head incident from the aperture. As a first step towards a characterisation of the spacecraft shielding effect (see Appendix A1) on the response functions of ERNE, we placed a roughly equivalent uniform 1 cm thick slab of ultra-dense aluminium (27 g/cm³) below the ERNE / HED model. We then simulated the response to backward penetrating particles. The resulting response functions are shown in Fig. 3. Finally, Fig. 4 shows the response of ERNE AC counters for penetrating relativistic protons coming from all directions.

2.2 EPHIN aboard SOHO

The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN, Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) is part of the suite Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer (COSTEP) onboard SOHO. It consists of a stack of six solid state detectors that is surrounded by a scintillation detector, which acts as an Anti-Coincidence (AC). Stopping ions are identified by applying the $\frac{dE}{dx} - E$ -method (for more details, see Heber et al. 2024). By utilising the $\frac{dE}{dx} - \frac{dE}{dx}$ method for hydrogen, helium, and electrons that pass the EPHIN detector stack, it was possible to extend the energy range of the instrument to energies up to several 100 MeV (Kühl et al. 2015, 2016, 2017; Heber et al. 2024).

¹<https://pyg4ometry.readthedocs.io>

Figure 2: Geant4-simulated responses of ERNE AC counters for forward penetrating relativistic protons for different energy deposit thresholds.

Figure 3: Geant4-simulated responses of ERNE AC counters for backward penetrating relativistic protons for different energy deposit thresholds.

3 Cross-calibration of ERNE with EPHIN

In order to obtain a realistic estimate of the energy deposit threshold of the ERNE AC counter (see Sect. 2.1.2), we perform a cross-calibration with SOHO / EPHIN. Because EPHIN is situated in close vicinity on the same spacecraft, both instruments are exposed to the same particle environment, significantly reducing uncertainties in cross-calibration. In D3.1 (Heber et al. 2024), EPHIN >100 MeV proton measurements have been compared with observations of the highly accurate Alpha Magnet Spectrometer (AMS-02, Aguilar et al. 2021), showing that these fluxes agree within 20% and that EPHIN measurements can indeed be used as a reference for ERNE. In the calibration carried out here, measured EPHIN proton spectra are folded with simulated ERNE response functions for different AC thresholds. These modelled ERNE count rates are then compared to actually measured ERNE count rates. Ideally, they agree for a specific energy threshold in the simulated ERNE AC response functions.

For the cross-calibration, observations of EPHIN and ERNE during different phases of two Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) events on 17 May 2012 and 1 Sep 2014 are used. ERNE count rate time series for different counters during these periods are shown in Fig. 5, with colour coded shadings indicating the periods for which EPHIN spectra (see Fig. 6) have been obtained. First, these spectra are corrected

Figure 4: Geant4-simulated responses of ERNE AC counters for penetrating relativistic protons coming from all directions for different energy deposit thresholds.

Figure 5: Count rates of ERNE counters AC1_TOT, AC1_D1E>1.3MeV, and D3, during 17 May 2012 (left) and 1 Sep 2014 (right) SEP events. Shaded areas indicate the time ranges used to calculate the corresponding EPHIN spectra shown in Figs. 6 and 7.

for the pre-event Galactic Cosmic Ray (GCR) background (black shading in Fig. 5 and black spectra in Fig. 6), resulting in background-subtracted spectra shown in Fig. 7. In addition, different types of spectral shapes are fitted to the background-subtracted spectra in order to have continuous functions for the further analysis. These fits have been obtained using a methodology that has been developed in a recent work analysing Solar Orbiter energy spectra (Fedeli et al. 2025). In this process, the energy spectra are fitted with five different functions (single power law, double power law, single power law with exponential cutoff, double power law with exponential cutoff, and triple power law; see Appendix A2 for equations), taking into account uncertainties both in energy ($\pm 10\%$ of the effective energy) and intensity. Afterwards, the best performing fit is selected based on their reduced χ^2 values. Figure 7 shows the found best fits to the background-subtracted EPHIN proton spectra and provides the fitting parameters in the legends.

Next, these fitted background-subtracted EPHIN proton spectra are folded with Geant4-simulated response functions of ERNE AC counters to calculate the corresponding modelled count rates. For this cross-calibration, response functions of penetrating protons incident from all directions are considered. Figure 8 shows the modelled ERNE count rates obtained with EPHIN spectrum from 02:00 to 03:00 on 17 May 2012 for different energy deposit thresholds in counters AC1_TOT and AC1_D1E>1.3MeV.

The modelled count rates are then normalized by dividing them by the averaged background-subtracted count rates observed by ERNE over the corresponding time interval of each spectrum. For the 2012

Figure 6: EPHIN proton spectra averaged over different periods during 17 May 2012 (left) and 1 Sep 2014 (right) SEP events. The periods are colour coded corresponding to the shaded regions in Fig. 5. The pre-event GCR background is shown by the black spectra in both plots.

Figure 7: EPHIN background-subtracted proton spectra averaged over different periods during 17 May 2012 (left) and 1 Sep 2014 (right) SEP events. The periods are colour coded corresponding to the shaded regions in Fig. 5. Different power laws have been fitted to the background-subtracted spectra; the type and parameters of the fits are listed in the legend (see Appendix A2 for details). Plotted on top as diamonds with the same colour coding are corresponding ERNE background-subtracted mean intensities that have been calculated using the geometric factor obtained at the end of Sect. 3.

Figure 8: ERNE counts rates obtained by folding Geant4-simulated response functions for different AC thresholds with EPHIN spectra obtained from 02:00 to 03:00 on 17 May 2012 for protons coming from all directions for counters AC1_TOT (left) and AC1_D1E>1.3MeV (right).

event, the background count rate observed by ERNE is obtained by averaging over the interval 00:00–02:00 on 17 May 2012, whereas for the 2014 event it is averaged over the interval 00:00–02:00 on 1 Sep 2014 (black shadings in Fig. 5). Figure 9 presents the normalized count rates for different spectra from May 2012 and Sep 2024 events, respectively.

Figure 9: ERNE normalized count rates corresponding to the simulated count rates divided by the average value of the background-subtracted observed count rates for counters AC1_TOT (left) and AC1_D1E>1.3MeV (right).

For counter AC1_TOT, the AC energy thresholds at which almost all modelled count rates are equal to the count rates observed by ERNE range from 8.27 to 9.34 MeV (Fig. 9, left). To examine whether this variation in AC thresholds correlates with a possible saturation of the ERNE instrument, these values are plotted against the observed count rates in Fig. 10. It shows no clear evidence of high count rate effects. We can mainly speculate about the reasons for the mismatch for the two time periods, but one of the possible reasons is flux anisotropy, which can cause ERNE and EPHIN to respond differently to a given energy spectrum. This could well be expected in the case of the first measured spectrum of the 17 May 2012 event, as it is obtained in the very onset phase of the event. Another reason could be that the backward penetrating particles are not yet very well modelled in ERNE. One issue could be simply the quality of the spectrum that is used to model the ERNE counting rate, which could be the main reason in particular in the time period of 03:00–06:00 during the 17–18 May 2012 event, as the statistics is clearly low and the errors are large in the data used for fitting (Fig. 7, yellow-coded spectrum on the left). Thus,

we will base further conclusions on the cross-calibration on the other five background-subtracted spectra in the analysis that show consistent results for the AC detection threshold.

Figure 10: For selected spectra, AC energy threshold value where the normalized count rate crosses 1 is plotted as a function of the ERNE average observed count rate for counter AC1_TOT.

For AC1_D1E > 1.3 MeV, no agreement between modelled and observed count rates can be found at all (Fig. 9, right). The most likely reason for this mismatch is the malfunctioning of the electronic comparator signal of the D1 energy loss (D1E > 1.3 MeV). During the early phase of the SOHO mission, a problem with this comparator signal was observed with particles stopping in the upper layers of the detector. Particles stopping in the stack produce pulse-height data for all detector layers (apart from the AC detectors) and the comparator signal can be compared with the actual registered pulse-height signal from the layer. This comparison showed that the comparator signal threshold is quite fuzzy, and the on-board software was updated not to take this comparator signal into account for the particles that are pulse-height analysed onboard to produce the science data products. However, as there is no possibility to correct for the AC counters that rely entirely on the comparator signals, we cannot apply a similar correction to this counter. Thus, we decided to discard the AC1_D1E > 1.3 MeV counter from further consideration in this project. In the future, it could be possible to try to model the comparator response, but since the uncertainty in the AC threshold is already a significant complication, we are not very optimistic about being able to determine the full response of the channel adequately.

The resulting simulated response functions of ERNE AC counters for the determined threshold range of 8.27 to 9.34 MeV for AC1_TOT are shown in Fig. 11. A differential bow-tie analysis has been performed on the response function for the lowest determined AC energy threshold 8.27 MeV (Fig. 12). The response function has been folded with a set of power-law spectra of the form $f(E) = A \cdot E^\alpha$, where the spectral index α varies from -4 to -2 . The effective differential geometric factors are calculated based on the following formula (Oleynik 2021, Sect. 5.3.3)²:

$$G\delta E(E_{\text{eff}}) = \frac{\int_0^\infty f(E) G(E) dE}{f(E_{\text{eff}})}, \quad (1)$$

where E_{eff} is the effective energy for a given spectrum $f(E)$. The optimal differential geometric factor and

²<https://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-951-29-8705-4>

Figure 11: Geant4-simulated responses of ERNE's AC1_TOT counter for penetrating relativistic protons coming from all directions for the energy deposit threshold range in which the modelled and observed ERNE count rates are in agreement.

effective energy located at the neck of the bow-tie are $877.9 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sr MeV}$ and 129.2 MeV , respectively, with an accuracy of 1%. Figure 13 presents the optimal differential geometric factor and effective energy at different AC energy threshold for counter AC1_TOT. The averaged, background-subtracted ERNE AC1_TOT counting rates are divided by this geometric factor and inserted in the EPHIN energy spectra in Fig. 7. As can be seen, apart from the spectrum taken during the onset of the 17 May 2012 event (2012-05-17T02:00–03:00, green diamond in left panel), all ERNE intensities agree with EPHIN measurements within the displayed error bars. This gives confidence on the applied cross-calibration method.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

We have considered the penetrating particle counters of ERNE / HED instrument in an attempt to cross-calibrate them with spectral data from SOHO / EPHIN. The task in the cross-calibration was to determine the best fit value of the AC detector threshold, which is unknown so far. We concluded that one of the counters is most likely unreliable due to a malfunctioning comparator signal in the counter logic, but another one could be utilised for scientific analysis with much better confidence. The best-fit detection threshold in the AC detectors is relatively large ($\sim 8.3 \text{ MeV}$) but seems to produce a good comparison with EPHIN spectra. We will proceed to generate a dataset of $\sim 130\text{-MeV}$ protons using the effective energy and differential geometric factor values for the ERNE penetrating particle channel obtained from this analysis.

In the future, we plan to revisit the analysis once the evaluation of backward-penetrating protons in ERNE is more firmly established. A GDML model of the SOHO spacecraft has already been created, and the next step will be a sectorised analysis of the spacecraft mass located beneath the instrument (see Appendix A1). The public release of the $\sim 130\text{-MeV}$ proton observations will take place after the current analysis is updated with the revised spacecraft model. Any resulting modifications to the present findings will be documented in a dedicated manuscript.

Figure 12: Bow-tie analysis of the ERNE simulated response functions for protons coming from all directions at AC energy threshold 8.27 MeV, corresponding to the lowest threshold where the normalized count rate crosses 1 for counter AC1_TOT. The upper panel shows the response function in blue (in arbitrary units) and the derived bow-tie formed by the family of differential effective geometric factors $G\delta E$ for different power-law indices (from -4 to -2). The lower panel shows the statistical measure of the bow-tie spreading in standard-deviation units normalized to the deviation of $G\delta E$ at the effective energy E_{eff} .

Figure 13: Differential geometric factor and effective energy of ERNE simulated response functions for protons coming from all directions at different AC energy threshold for counter AC1_TOT.

Bibliography

- Aguilar, M., Cavazonza, L. A., Ambrosi, G., et al. 2021, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 127, 271102
- Boogert, S., Abramov, A., Nevay, L., et al. 2025, *pyg4ometry*
- Fedeli, A., Dresing, N., Gieseler, J., et al. 2025, *A&A*, in revision
- Heber, B., Hörlock, M., Köberle, M., Kühl, P., & Papaioannou, A. 2024, Deliverable 3.1: Cross-calibration of SOHO / EPHIN with spectrometer data, Report, SPEARHEAD Project
- Kühl, P., Banjac, S., Dresing, N., et al. 2015, *A&A*, 576, A120
- Kühl, P., Dresing, N., Heber, B., & Klassen, A. 2017, *Sol. Phys.*, 292, 10
- Kühl, P., Gómez-Herrero, R., & Heber, B. 2016, *Sol. Phys.*, 291, 965
- Köberle, M., Heber, B., Kühl, P., et al. 2024, Deliverable 2.1: Geant4 models, part I, Report, SPEARHEAD Project
- Köberle, M., Heber, B., Kühl, P., et al. 2025, Deliverable 2.3: Simulated response functions, part I, Report, SPEARHEAD Project
- Müller-Mellin, R., Kunow, H., Fleißner, V., et al. 1995, *Sol. Phys.*, 162, 483
- Oleynik, P. 2021, Phd thesis, University of Turku, Turku, Finland
- Valtonen, E., Peltonen, J., Peltonen, P., et al. 1997, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 391, 249
- Walker, S., Abramov, A., Nevay, L., Shields, W., & Boogert, S. 2022, *Computer Physics Communications*, 272, 108228

Appendix

A1 SOHO spacecraft model

In addition to the instrument head, we reconstructed a 3-D model of the SOHO spacecraft. We will use the same method as described in Sect. 2.4.2 of D2.3 (Köberle et al. 2025) to construct a shield (like the one shown in Fig. 6 of D2.3) equivalent to the passive structure surrounding the sensitive head of the instrument. We aim to represent the spacecraft as a compact sectored spherical shell with a thickness corresponding to the amount of passive spacecraft material along each direction. Currently, the GDML model of SOHO is prepared for Geantino scanning as illustrated in Fig. 14. (A Geantino is a non-interacting virtual particle in Geant4 that can be used to record the amount of material along its path.)

Figure 14: A Geant4 visualisation of the SOHO spacecraft model with ERNE onboard. In the right panel, the yellow piece on the top with red spots is the ERNE sensor unit.

A2 Energy spectrum fitting

Following Fedeli et al. (2025), to find the best fit for an EPHIN energy spectrum, the data is fitted (including uncertainties in energy and intensity) to five different functions:

- single power law (Eq. 2)
- double power law (Eq. 3)
- single power law with exponential cutoff (Eq. 4)
- double power law with exponential cutoff (Eq. 5)
- triple power law (Eq. 6)

The corresponding equations are:

$$I(E) = I_0 \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right)^{\gamma_1} \quad (2)$$

$$I(E) = I_0 \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right)^{\gamma_1} \left(\frac{E^\alpha + E_b^\alpha}{E_0^\alpha + E_b^\alpha} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_2 - \gamma_1}{\alpha}} \quad (3)$$

$$I(E) = I_0 \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right)^{\gamma_1} e^{-\left(\frac{E}{E_c}\right)^x} \quad (4)$$

$$I(E) = I_0 \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right)^{\gamma_1} \left(\frac{E^\alpha + E_b^\alpha}{E_0^\alpha + E_b^\alpha} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_2 - \gamma_1}{\alpha}} e^{-\left(\frac{E}{E_c}\right)^x} \quad (5)$$

$$I(E) = I_0 \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right)^{\gamma_1} \left(\frac{E^\alpha + E_{bl}^\alpha}{E_0^\alpha + E_{bl}^\alpha} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_2 - \gamma_1}{\alpha}} \left(\frac{E^\beta + E_{bh}^\beta}{E_0^\beta + E_{bh}^\beta} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_3 - \gamma_2}{\beta}}, \quad (6)$$

where E is energy, I intensity, I_0 intensity defined at the reference energy $E_0 = 0.1$ MeV, and γ_1 , γ_2 , α , x , E_c , E_b , E_{bl} , E_{bh} , γ_3 , and β are fitting parameters. Afterwards, the best fit per spectrum is selected by the lowest χ^2 value.